

EARTH SCIENCES

RADON EMISSION INVESTIGATION IN THE SHAMAKHI DISTRICT OF THE AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18841654>

Abstract

The naturally occurring radioactive inert gas radon (^{222}Rn) is formed in the uranium decay series. It is a significant radiation risk factor for the population and a promising geochemical indicator of tectonic activity. This paper examines radon emissions and monitoring at a seismological station and wells in the Shamakhi region and the Absheron Peninsula of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The geomorphology of the Shamakhi region is also studied.

Keywords: radon, emission, radiation risk, monitoring, geomorphology

Introduction

Radon (Rn) is a noble radioactive gas with atomic number 86. The most important isotope is ^{222}Rn (half-life $T_{1/2} = 3.82$ days), formed in the decay chain of uranium ^{238}U . According to the World Health Organization, radon is the second leading cause of lung cancer after smoking. Radon also serves as a sensitive indicator of changes in the stress state of the Earth's crust.

The main nuclear decay chain:

Radon activity is determined by the formula:

$$A = \lambda N$$

here: A is the activity (Bq), λ is the decay constant, N is the number of atoms.

Decay constant is:

$$\lambda = \frac{\ln 2}{T_{1/2}}$$

Geomorphology of the Greater and Lesser Caucasus

The geomorphology of Shamakhi region is characterized by a complex mountainous relief located on the southeastern slope of the Greater Caucasus. The territory consists of high mountains, intermountain depressions and foothill zones of the Greater Caucasus Range (Dubrar, Gulumdostu, 2200-2700 m), as well as high seismic activity and widespread erosion-denudation processes (slabs, avalanches).

The main features of the relief:

- High and Middle Highlands: In the northern part, the height exceeds 2000 meters (Carlica Mountain - 2714 m), the relief is steep, the valleys are deep.

- Intermountain Depressions: In the center of the region, intermountain depressions belonging to the Shamakhi-Gobustan synclinorium, which have been subjected to denudation processes (for example, the Shamakhi Depression), are located.

- Frontal and Low Highlands: The height decreases towards the southeast (Gijek - 1047 m), the rocks become younger (Neogene clays), and erosive relief forms prevail.

- Rock Structure: Cretaceous limestones are widespread in the north, and Paleogene-Neogene clays

and sandstones in the south, which also affects the formation of the relief.

- Borders: The relief of the region is surrounded by mountain ranges in the north (Pirdirayi, Qiz Qalasy), and river valleys in the south (Zogalavay).

The Shamakhi region has a constantly changing, fragmented relief under the influence of intensive tectonic movements.

Radon emissions in Absheron

Radon (Rn) gas analysis was carried out in the groundwater of the Absheron seismic zone ("Shikhov-2", "Surakhani" facilities) at the "Bibi-Heybat" geochemical station. Water samples were taken once a day, 5 days a week. The measuring equipment used was the "Alpharad plus" radiometer, included in the list of devices in the state register (database 49013-12). The radiometer is characterized by a relative error limit of $\pm 30\%$.

1) Well "Shamakhi No. 8", depth 100-200 m, water composition - layered water, hydrosulfide, cold ($t^{\circ}\text{C} = 13\div 14$), low-mineralized, Kurlov formula is

$$pH_{7,8} Eh_{+80} M_{0,6} \frac{HCO_{54}^3 \sum Cl_{28}^- SO_{19}^4}{\sum Na_{53} Mg_{35} Ca_{12}}$$

2) Well "Chukhuryurd No. 49", depth 100-200 m, water composition - fractured, hydrosulfide, subthermal ($t^{\circ}\text{C} = 16-24$), Kurlov formula is

$$pH_{8,9} Eh_{-195} M_{1,4} \frac{(HCO_{43}^3 CO_{14}^3) SO_{28}^4 \sum Cl_{15}^-}{\sum Na_{93}}$$

Seismofluidgeochemical (SFGD) studies are presented by studying the regime of fluids in the seismically active zones of the southern (Shamakhi, Sheki regions) and northeastern (Khachmaz, Siyazan regions) slopes of the Greater Caucasus megaanticlinorium, its southeastern end (Absheron Peninsula), and at the same time the Azerbaijani part of Talysh (Lankaran region). 6 stationary geochemical stations operate in the indicated areas: "Bibi-Heybat" geochemical station (Baku city); "Shamakhi" geochemical station (Shamakhi district); "Sheki" geochemical station (Sheki district); "Osakuja"

geochemical station (Lankaran district); “Boyuk-Hamya” geochemical station (Siyazan district); “Mukhtadir” geochemical station (Khachmaz district). Fluid observation objects differ in terms of the genesis of hydrogeochemical parameters and migration conditions.

The study of seismic activity and its relationship to parameters measured on the Earth's surface is an important task of seismology. Over the past decades, scientists have been trying to develop methods for predicting earthquakes. Particular attention is paid to the search for precursors, among which radon anomalies and magnetic field fluctuations stand out as potentially significant. In addition, increasing computing power and the development of artificial intelligence methods open up new opportunities for analyzing complex multifactorial data.

Current research highlights the need for sophisticated systems capable of collecting, processing, and interpreting data in real time. This is especially relevant for regions with high seismic activity, such as the Caucasus region. The development of autonomous systems capable of operating in remote and hard-to-reach areas is becoming a key area of modern seismology. Such systems allow for real-time monitoring without human intervention, minimizing risks, and increasing response speed.

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The developed complex consists of detector blocks, interface, control block, internet channel block, device for receiving data from the seismic center, device for receiving data on the current state of solar activity, analysis unit based on artificial intelligence and decision-making, and autonomous power supply unit on solar panels. The detector units include radon radioactive gas detector and magnetometer devices for measuring the strength of the magnetic field in a given area.

Radon as a harbinger of earthquakes

A number of authors claim that before strong events, the following are observed:

- an increase in soil air concentration
- a change in the daily amplitude
- sharp anomalous emissions
- a correlation with the b-value.

The b-value is a coefficient that shows the relationship between the number of small and large earthquakes in a given region over a period of time (Gutenberg-Richter Law).

In a quiet subsurface, the b-value is typically close to 1.0.

○ If $b = 1$, this means that earthquakes with a magnitude of 4 will be 10 times fewer than those with a magnitude of 3.

○ A low b-value may indicate the accumulation of high stress in a fault, which sometimes precedes large tremors.

Possible mechanisms for this phenomenon are:

1. Increased tectonic stress
2. Formation of microcracks
3. Increased degassing
4. Release of deep radon.

Radon in Azerbaijan (Ismayilli, Shamakhi)

The southern slope of the Greater Caucasus is characterized by:

- active faults
- intense folding
- uranium-bearing rocks

The Ismayilly region is characterized by:

- increased fracturing
- active hydrogeodynamics
- possible radon anomalies before local earthquakes

Monitoring was conducted under the following conditions:

1. Boreholes 30–70 m
2. Continuous radon sensors
3. Temperature and pressure correction
4. Comparison with seismicity ($ML \geq 3$)

The integral geodynamic normalized index was studied:

$$I = \omega_1 Z_{Rn} + \omega_2 Z_b + \omega_3 Z_{EM}$$

here Z is the standardized parameters (z-score).

Data processing program in Python

Loading and filtering:

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.stats import zscore
# data input
data = pd.read_csv("radon_data.csv",
parse_dates=["date"])
# outlier removal
data["radon_filtered"] = data["radon"].rolling(24).mean()
# calculation z-score
data["radon_z"] = zscore(data["radon_filtered"]).dropna()
Plotting radon emission graphs:
plt.figure()
plt.plot(data["date"], data["radon_filtered"])
plt.xlabel("Date")
plt.ylabel("Radon (Bq/m3)")
plt.title("Radon concentration dynamics")
plt.show()
Расчет b-value:
def b_value(magnitudes):
    return np.log10(np.e) / (np.mean(magnitudes) -
np.min(magnitudes))
magnitudes = np.array([3.1,3.5,3.8,4.0,4.2])
b = b_value(magnitudes)
print ("b-value:", b)
Calculation of the integral index
data["b_z"] = zscore(data["b_value"])
data["index"] = 0.4*data["radon_z"] +
0.4*data["b_z"]
plt.figure()
```

```
plt.plot(data["date"], data["index"])
plt.xlabel("Date")
plt.ylabel("Integrated Index")
plt.show()
```

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This work was supported by the Azerbaijan Sciences Foundation – Grant № AEF-BQM-BRFTF-4-2024-5(53)-06/03/2-M-03